

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-
london-interactions-bank
hash://md5/4ea2bf4f67fd19528081764d377c287e

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank>

2026-01-29

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank, has fingerprint hash://md5/4ea2bf4f67fd19528081764d377c287e, is 80.6MiB in size and contains 242,477 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., parasiteOf) between 30,260 primary taxa (e.g., Trichogramma) and 35,764 associated taxa (e.g., Citrus). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Ed Baker; Ian J. Kitching; George W. Beccaloni; Amoret Whitaker et al. (2016). Dataset: NHM Interactions Bank. Natural History Museum Data Portal (data.nhm.ac.uk). <https://doi.org/10.5519/0060767>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank/archive/0385e7b8c3f9681042f3edda7bd1d2c3766feb29.zip>
2026-01-24T04:57:31.617Z hash://md5/4ea2bf4f67fd19528081764d377c287e

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer

(Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.4
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 80.6MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/natural-history-museum-london-interactions-bank`, has fingerprint hash://md5/4ea2bf4f67fd19528081764d377c287e, is 80.6MiB in size and contains 242,477 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., `parasiteOf`) between 30,260 primary taxa (e.g., `Trichogramma`) and 35,764 associated taxa (e.g., `Citrus`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Lonchodes jejunus	eats	Ixonanthes reticulata	F. Seow-Choen, A Taxonomic Guide to the Stick Insects of Borneo. Kota Kinabalu: Natural History Publications (Borneo), 2016.
Lonchodes jejunus	eats	Psychotria	F. Seow-Choen, A Taxonomic Guide to the Stick Insects of Borneo. Kota Kinabalu: Natural History Publications (Borneo), 2016.
Lonchodes jejunus	eats	Psidium guajava	F. Seow-Choen, A Taxonomic Guide to the Stick Insects of Borneo. Kota Kinabalu: Natural History Publications (Borneo), 2016.
Lonchodes jejunus	eats	Rubus moluccanus	F. Seow-Choen, A Taxonomic Guide to the Stick Insects of Borneo. Kota Kinabalu: Natural History Publications (Borneo), 2016.

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
parasiteOf	155862
eats	65170
ectoparasiteOf	21396
vectorOf	25
adjacentTo	23
parasitoidOf	1

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Trichogramma	1612
Encarsia formosa	1183
Trichogramma chilonis	961
Trichogramma evanescens	954
Tetrastichus	951
Dibrachys microgastri	943
Trichogramma minutum	919
Trichogramma pretiosum	873
Ceratophyllus Ceratophyllus gallinae	735
Eurytoma	698
Eupelmus urozonus	670
Encarsia citrina	645
Cirrospilus vittatus	620
Dasypsyllus Dasypsyllus gallinulae gallinulae	612
Sympiesis sericeicornis	601
Sympiesis gordius	587
Eupelmus vesicularis	547
Pteromalus	520
Chrysocharis nephereus	517

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Citrus	2342
Quercus	1562

targetTaxonName	count
Salix	1223
Malus pumila	1015
Saissetia oleae	873
Saccharum officinarum	871
Oryza sativa	845
Zea mays	844
Trialeurodes vaporariorum	829
Prunus	779
Aonidiella aurantii	778
Bemisia tabaci	735
Gossypium	728
Coffea	711
Theobroma cacao	694
Musca domestica	691
Phyllocnistis citrella	658
Coccus hesperidum	649
Populus	642

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Encarsia formosa	parasiteOf	Trialeurodes vaporariorum	515
Spilopsyllus cuniculi	ectoparasiteOf	Oryctolagus cuniculus	250
Aphytis melinus	parasiteOf	Aonidiella aurantii	173
Anagyrus lopezi	parasiteOf	Phenacoccus manihoti	144
Encarsia formosa	parasiteOf	Lycopersicon esculentum	144
Aphelinus mali	parasiteOf	Eriosoma lanigerum	129
Leptomastix dactylopii	parasiteOf	Planococcus citri	122
Pulex Pulex irritans	ectoparasiteOf	Homo sapiens	119
Encarsia perniciosi	parasiteOf	Quadraspidotus perniciosus	114
Archaeopsylla erinacei	ectoparasiteOf	Erinaceus europaeus	113

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Ceratophyllus Ceratophyllus hirundinis	ectoparasiteOf	Delichon urbica	111
Comperiella bifasciata	parasiteOf	Aonidiella aurantii	103
Muscidifurax raptor	parasiteOf	Musca domestica	103
Ceratophyllus Ceratophyllus farreni farreni	ectoparasiteOf	Delichon urbica	102
Eretmocerus mundus	parasiteOf	Bemisia tabaci	102
Trichogramma brassicae	parasiteOf	Ostrinia nubilalis	102
Encarsia formosa	parasiteOf	Bemisia tabaci	97
Ischnopsyllus Ischnopsyllus octactenus	ectoparasiteOf	Pipistrellus pipistrellus	95
Ctenocephalides canis	ectoparasiteOf	Canis familiaris	93

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Pluvialis obscura	NONE	col	Pluvialis obscura
Lobesia helichrysana	SYNONYM_OF	col	Lobesia cinerariae
Butorides plumbeus	NONE	col	Butorides plumbeus
Elbella polyzona	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Elbella polyzona

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	12369
col	class	1
col	family	96
col	form	2
col	genus	4275
col	infraspecific name	3
col	order	9
col	phylum	1
col	section	1
col	species	43918
col	subfamily	5
col	subgenus	120
col	suborder	2
col	subspecies	2185
col	superfamily	2
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	4
col	variety	222
discoverlife	NA	62423
discoverlife	species	202

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
gbif	NA	7910
gbif	class	1
gbif	family	110
gbif	form	14
gbif	genus	4504
gbif	order	7
gbif	phylum	2
gbif	species	48102
gbif	subspecies	2401
gbif	variety	267
itis	NA	44399
itis	class	1
itis	division	1
itis	family	96
itis	form	1
itis	genus	2460
itis	order	9
itis	phylum	2
itis	species	14099
itis	subfamily	11
itis	subgenus	7
itis	suborder	3
itis	subspecies	1466
itis	superfamily	1
itis	superorder	1
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	97
mdd	NA	62625
ncbi	NA	33198
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	2
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	98
ncbi	genus	3929
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	order	7
ncbi	phylum	1
ncbi	section	4
ncbi	species	24716
ncbi	subfamily	14
ncbi	subgenus	51
ncbi	suborder	1
ncbi	subspecies	570
ncbi	superfamily	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	1
ncbi	varietas	62
pbdb	NA	59090
pbdb	class	1
pbdb	family	98
pbdb	genus	1261
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	infraorder	2
pbdb	order	9
pbdb	phylum	2
pbdb	species	2124
pbdb	subfamily	11
pbdb	subgenus	2
pbdb	suborder	4
pbdb	subspecies	21
pbdb	superfamily	2
pbdb	superorder	2
pbdb	tribe	2
pbdb	unranked clade	4
tpt	NA	54128
tpt	family	19
tpt	genus	95
tpt	order	2
tpt	species	8383
wfo	NA	50793
wfo	family	11
wfo	form	1
wfo	genus	1906
wfo	section	2
wfo	species	9646
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	285
wfo	variety	167
worms	NA	57930
worms	class	1
worms	family	78
worms	genus	1267
worms	order	8
worms	phylum	1
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	3267
worms	subgenus	1
worms	suborder	3

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	subspecies	91
worms	superorder	1
worms	variety	16

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	13501
col	SYNONYM_OF	17614
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	54445
discoverlife	NONE	74673
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	169
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	15
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	70
gbif	NONE	8450
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	23689
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	61889
itis	NONE	53109
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	19051
itis	SYNONYM_OF	3250
mdd	NONE	72912
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1945
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	20
ncbi	NONE	38041
ncbi	SAME_AS	33786
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	3324
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	1
pbdb	NONE	70309
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4386
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	324
tpt	NONE	65124
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	2594
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7832
wfo	NONE	60616
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	11611
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	4613

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1295
worms	NONE	68698
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6041
worms	SYNONYM_OF	1027

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-29T04:35:06Z	note	found [46] columns, but only [24] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.
2026-01-29T04:35:06Z	note	found [46] columns, but only [24] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.
2026-01-29T04:35:06Z	note	found [46] columns, but only [24] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.
2026-01-29T04:35:06Z	note	found [46] columns, but only [24] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found [46] columns, but only [24] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.	350346
source taxon name missing	100832
target taxon name missing	7033
found unsupported interaction type with name: [does not eat]	3

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-29) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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